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stable carbon sinks in soil environments**

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ABSTRACT

In addition to many other processes, external organic material can be thermo-chemically converted with the aim of hygienization, stabilization of carbon compounds and the achievement of desired properties to improve soil properties. The solid product of thermo-chemical conversion ($>>350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the absence of molecular oxygen (pyrolysis) of biomass is called biochar. Thermochemical conversion at lower temperatures under high pressure (hydrothermal processes) results in a solid product called hydrochar.

The analysis of physico-chemical parameters of these products is necessary to guarantee a standardized product quality as a precondition for public trust. Above all, the soil application of external organic matter, including thermochemical conversion products, must follow the principle “do no harm”. Therefore, international guidelines have summarized limit values for quality parameters of soil additives that are important when the products are applied to soil as fertilizers, amendments or for carbon sequestration. Such limits values prevent contamination with potentially toxic trace elements (“heavy metals”) or organic pollutants and take care of shifts in basic soil characteristics that might interfere with soil organisms. Legally binding limit values for “pyrolysis and gasification material” (= biochar) are provided by the Regulation (EU) 2019/1009. In additions, the “Guidelines for sustainable biochar production” of the European Biochar Certificate (EBC) are the established international standard for high quality biochar and its characterization, however it is not legally binding. Hydrochars are not approved as an EU fertilizer product, so there are no binding limit values.

This report provides an overview on analytical methods that should be applied in routine analysis of biochar for quality assurance. Further on, this report also summarizes analytical methods that are important for scientific analyses of thermochemical conversion products to explain their effects on the environment. Special attention is given to nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy as a powerful tool for investigating individual functional groups.

Biochar characteristics are determined by both feedstock selection and the processing conditions. The desire to produce biochars tailor-made for specific application purposes have led to the development of mixtures of different input materials, including non-plant feedstock. A promising mixture consists of sewage sludge and lignocellulosic input material that facilitates the production of biochars that are both useful for carbon sequestration and for recycling of nutrients that otherwise would be lost in mono-incineration of sewage sludge. In those countries where agricultural use of sewage sludge is still possible but faces resistance, the production of biochar from sewage sludge provides additional utilization pathways for both nutrients and carbon.

Mean residence time of carbon in thermochemical conversion products applied to soil may vary from few decades to several millennia. Generally, products of hydrothermal carbonization are less resistant to mineralization than pyrolysis products. Hydrochars in soil usually will be degraded after a few decades, biochars only after centuries to millennia. Important parameters affecting carbon mean residence time in soil are the pyrolysis reactor design, gas flow, biochar particle size and the connection of biochar with clay minerals. Pre- or post-pyrolysis modifications can positively influence the biochar carbon stability. For proper calculation of a biochar-based carbon sink that is required for trading platforms and for carbon accounting, a complete survey of the greenhouse gas emissions during biomass production and transport before pyrolysis is required, followed by a precise consideration of carbon losses during pyrolysis and prior to incorporation into soil.

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1 Analytical methods to characterize thermochemical conversion products: Biochar-analyses for routine analysis

Analysis methods must be selected according to the matrix. Pyrolysis products differ significantly from other external organic matter that are used as fertilizers or soil additives in agriculture and therefore form a special matrix. This was investigated in more detail by Bachmann et al. (2016) and suitable analysis methods were proposed by a round robin test between laboratories in Europe. These methods have been adopted both in the guidelines of the European Biochar Certificate (EBC 2012), a private standard for the quality assurance of biochar, and in the Austrian standard ÖNORM S 2211. The work of the German standards ("DIN") committee NA 062-02-85 "Pyrogenic carbonaceous materials" is also based on this; however, this standard for the definition of biochar has not yet been published here. Although the EU Fertilizer Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 defines limit values specifically for biochar (CMC 14), it does not yet specify any analytical requirements. The "European Committee for Standardization" has now been tasked with this.

Particular attention needs to be paid to the quantification of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), a group of pollutants that are inevitably produced in the pyrolysis process and whose condensation on the biochar can be effectively prevented by suitable process control. Biochar is a good sorbent for non-polar substances such as PAHs, so the extraction process, which is the foundation of any analysis, must be adapted in order to determine the content appropriately. The use of toluene as an extraction agent and a sufficiently long extraction time in the Soxhlet extraction apparatus are crucial (Hilber, Bastos, et al. 2017; Hilber et al. 2012; Hilber, Mayer, et al. 2017; Buss et al. 2022). Thus, the European Biochar Certificate requires analysis according extraction method 10.2.3 with toluene of the DIN EN 17503. In deviation from the standard (2 h), an extraction time of 6 h is required. The EU Regulation 2019/1009, the ÖNORM S 2211 and the EBC define a limit value of 6 mg kg⁻¹ for agricultural use. The Swiss ordinance on fertilization defines a limit value of 4 mg kg⁻¹.

In addition to PAHs, biochar is characterized in practice primarily by its carbon and ash content and by the molar element ratio of hydrogen to organic carbon (molar H/C_{org} ratio). The EU Regulation 2019/1009, the ÖNORM S 2211 and the EBC requires a molar H/C_{org} ratio of <0.7. In Table 1 the list of parameters required by EBC is given alongside with the respective analytical standard.

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Table 1: Commonly used analytical techniques that are also required by analysis according to the European Biochar Certificate (EBC, 2012)

Method / Analyte	Standard	Comment
Sample preparation	DIN 51701-3	Biochar should be dried at 40 °C, not higher
Bulk density	VDLUFA-Method A 13.2.1	
Salt content / electric conductivity	DIN ISO 11265	
pH	DIN ISO 10390	
Water content	DIN 51718	
Ash content	DIN 51719	
Carbonate content	DIN 51726	The distinction between organic and inorganic carbon is important for the calculation of permanent carbon storage, as only organic carbon is considered here.
Elemental analysis CHN	DIN 51732	
Sulphur content	DIN 51724-3	
Oxygen content	DIN 51733	The oxygen content can be measured directly for scientific purposes, but for routine analysis this is not considered appropriate and the oxygen content is calculated.
PAH content	DIN EN 17503 (extraction method 10.2.3 using toluol)	The EBC requires an extraction time of 6 hours (instead of 2 hours)

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Method / Analyte	Standard	Comment
Trace metals (Pb, Cd, Cu, Ni, Hg, Zn, Cr, B, Mn, As, Ag)	DIN 22022-2, DIN 22022-7, DIN EN ISO 17294-2 / DIN EN 1483:	microwave-assisted digestion
Main elements (P, Mg, Ca, K, Na, Fe, Si, S)	DIN 51729-11, DIN EN ISO 11885 / DIN EN ISO 17294-2	ICP-OES after melting digestion
Water holding capacity	DIN EN ISO 14238, annex A	
Electrical conductivity of the solid biochar	Black Gauß https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8197758	The electrical conductivity enables a quick and easy investigation of carbon speciation, as a higher aromaticity of the biochar leads to a higher conductivity. Standardization is planned as part of the DIN project NA 062-02-85.

2 Analytical methods to characterize thermochemical conversion products: Research-oriented analyses for scientific questions

2.1 Biochar characterization by advanced analytical methods - overview

For scientific purposes, many different sophisticated analytical methods may be applied that may help to understand the behavior and characteristics of biochar. The following list shows some examples of advanced analytical methods to characterize biochar in more detail (Table 2).

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Table 2 : Advanced analytical techniques for the characterization of biochar. For further information see Singh et al., 2017.

Method	Purpose
Analysis of benzene polycarboxylic acids	Molecular marker for the existence of biochar
Pyrolysis-GC-MS	Identification of a large number of pyrolysis products as indicator for the degree of thermochemical conversion
Solid-state ¹³ C-NMR	Characterization of aromaticity (sorption affinity for non-polar sorbates)
Fourier-transform-infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy	Characterization of biochar surface functional groups
X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy	Biochar surface chemistry and composition
X-ray diffraction analysis	Identification of crystalline or amorphous phases
Stable isotope analysis	Stable isotope ratios of light elements for elemental tracking
Gas adsorption (N ₂ or other inert gases)	Specific surface area
Mercury porosimetry, pycnometry	Porosity, pore size distribution
Scanning electron microscopy	Information about elemental composition
Thermogravimetric analysis	Mass changes of the sample during controlled heating
Boehm titration	Characterization of acidic functional groups on biochar surface
Cation exchange capacity	Analysis of the ability to adsorb cations in exchangeable form

2.2 Biochar characterization by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR)

One of the main concerns to understand biochar's physical chemistry is the right procedure to be used in order to unveil its properties. Among the different techniques that can be applied (Conte et al.,

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2021), nuclear magnetic resonance appears to be the most suitable (Conte et al., 2024). The term “nuclear magnetic resonance” encompasses a diverse range of techniques, each offering distinct types of information while being all of them based on the same principles (Abragam, 1983). NMR spectroscopy, for instance, is utilized to assess molecular structures and conformations (Silverstein et al., 2005); magnetic resonance imaging finds application in diagnosing health issues (Sataloff et al., 2015), monitoring water dynamics in environmental compartments (Pohlmeier, 2011), plants, and foods (Van As and Van Duynhoven, 2013); NMR diffusimetry is employed to investigate fluid transport through porous media (Stallmach and Kärger, 1999), while fast field cycling (FFC) NMR relaxometry is utilized to study molecular dynamics in proteins (Kruk et al., 2019; Kimmich and Anzardo, 2004), food systems (Baroni et al., 2009; Godefroy et al., 2003; Conte et al., 2009; Conte et al., 2021; Conte et al., 2011; Conte et al., 2010), new materials (Lo Meo et al., 2020), and environmental systems (Conte and Lo Meo, 2020).

The different types of NMR techniques can be divided into two groups: high- and low-field resolution. In the realm of NMR terminology, the expression “low-resolution” or “LR-NMR” denotes an ensemble of techniques that yield spectra with limited or no resolution. Spectra lacking resolution are characterized by broad and overlapping signals, where individual multiplets are indiscernible. The convolution of signals from various nuclei resonances results in a merged signal, making accurate assignments challenging, if not impossible. Enhancing NMR resolution involves the use of special care. For instance, NMR resolution can be ameliorated by the enhancement of the magnetic field. Consequently, what is presently termed high-resolution NMR may be considered low-resolution in the future as a result of the ongoing technical advancements. It is essential, however, to ensure that technical improvements do not overcome the radiofrequency limits (0.3 Hz –3 THz) within which NMR operates. Conventionally, LR-NMR is defined as a technique where the magnetic field strength ranges from 4×10^{-5} T (equivalent to the Earth's magnetic field) up to 2.5 T. Nuclear relaxation remains unaffected by spectral resolution. Consequently, LR-NMR techniques can be utilized to assess the relaxation characteristics of intricate systems where high resolution is unnecessary. An additional benefit is that LR-NMR enables the observation of slow motions that are not perceptible when strong magnetic fields are employed (Conte et al., 2024).

After nuclear excitation, relaxation takes place. The timeframe of nuclear relaxation is contingent upon the molecular size and the physical state of the system being examined. The mechanisms of relaxation entail local magnetic fields, shaped by the electronic and atomic surroundings, which are influenced by molecular motions. Relaxation occurs when the Larmor frequency of these local magnetic fields resonates with that of the observed nuclei. Nuclear relaxation is due to two distinct mechanisms. The first, known as longitudinal relaxation, involves the restoration of the magnetization equilibrium along the applied magnetic field (B_0) direction (typically the z-axis of a xyz-space), accompanied by the loss

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of energy quanta. The second process, termed as transverse relaxation, arises from the loss of phase coherence and the decline of excited magnetization perpendicular to B_0 . The time parameter associated to the longitudinal relaxation is denoted as T_1 . It is also known as longitudinal relaxation time. The time constant for transverse relaxation is indicated as T_2 and is commonly referred to as transverse relaxation time.

After configuring NMR experiments to measure relaxation times (either T_1 or T_2), the time-evolving resonance signals can be processed using the inverse Laplace transform. This process yields relaxograms (either 1D or 2D), providing representations of the distribution of relaxation times (Boriga et al., 1998; Borgia et al., 2000; Borgia et al., 2001; Bortololotti et al., 2017; Bortolotti et al., 2018). This method, also known as time-domain (TD) NMR, is employed to elucidate the molecular dynamics of complex systems under a constant magnetic field strength (Conte, 2019). When an experiment is made in low-field resolution by quickly changing the proton Larmor frequency of the applied magnetic field (that is, fast field cycling NMR relaxometry), the profiles known as nuclear magnetic resonance dispersion (NMRD) are obtained (Kimmich and Anoardo, 2004; Kimmich, 1979). These profiles depict how the longitudinal relaxation rate ($R_1=1/T_1$) changes as the intensity of the applied magnetic field is rapidly altered across different values. This method is employed to assess molecular motions within the time scale of 10^{-8} to 10^{-3} seconds, covering the range from slow tumbling to slow diffusion (Kimmich and Anoardo, 2004). In comparison to other NMR techniques, the distinctive feature of FFC NMR relaxometry is its heightened sensitivity to the aforementioned molecular motions, facilitated by the unique design of the hardware system (Anoardo et al., 2001).

FFC NMR relaxometry, being a low field technique (Conte, 2019), can be considered the most powerful technique to unveil biochar's characteristics (Conte et al., 2024). In fact, all the other high field NMR techniques are subjected to many limitations such as poor biochar solubility that prevents the application of liquid state NMR technique; poor proton concentration that reduces cross polarization magic angle spinning (CPMAS) NMR sensitivity; bad biochar packaging in solid state NMR rotors, responsible for asymmetrical fast rotation, thereby causing NMR probe damage; high biochar electrical conductivity – related to its aromatic nature – that may cause eddy currents. The latter are responsible for the incorrect tuning and matching of the NMR probe and, in the worst cases, for the arcing phenomenon that can be responsible for the probe burning. A more complete list of the different limitations of high field NMR techniques can be found in Conte et al. (2024).

The application of NMR to the samples prepared in the frame of EOM4SOIL will be described in a journal article that is currently in preparation.

3 Co-pyrolysis of sewage sludge with lignocellulosic feedstocks: feedstock effects on carbonization product stability

Biochar is the carbon dense material obtained from pyrolysis of biomasses or organic solid wastes, and is recently gaining more and more interest as a bio-fertilizer for soil and a mitigator of greenhouse emissions (Deng et al., 2021; Keskinen et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2013). According to EBC (Schmidt, 2015) biochar is a heterogeneous substance rich in aromatic carbon and minerals. It is produced by pyrolysis of sustainably obtained biomass under controlled conditions with clean technology and is used for any purpose that does not involve its rapid mineralization to CO₂, and may eventually become a soil amendment. Pyrolysis is thermal decomposition of the feedstocks under absent oxygen or air atmosphere to produce the bio-oil, biochar and pyrolysis gas, depending on pyrolysis types. Slow pyrolysis is widely used to produce biochar with high product yield and quality. During this process, the physical and chemical properties of the feedstocks become a highly porous, stable, and carbon-rich material (biochar) with a vast surface area (Turunen et al., 2023, 2021). Biochar can be produced from various types of biomasses, such as agricultural residues and wastes (woods, sawdust, straws, and peels), industrial organic wastes, organic municipal solid wastes, and sewage sludge from wastewater treatment systems in all over the globe.

Sewage sludge (SS) contains a large quantity of organic matter, as well as valuable nutrients like N, P and K, which are elements that can be reused in soil for increasing crop productivity as fertilizer after proper recycling process. Sewage Sludge obtained from municipal and industrial wastewater treatment has potential to be used as a source of both bioenergy and valuable compounds, following the concept of circular bioeconomy. Degradation using thermal processes helps to increase the value of low-grade biomasses and organic wastes such as SS (Phoungthong et al., 2018; Phoungthong and Suwunwong, 2020). Turning SS into biochar provides new utilization solutions for countries where SS use in agriculture is restricted by either legislation or farmers' attitudes.

The properties of SS biochars depend on many factors, such type of SS, condition for producing biochar, and type of reactor (Rehman et al., 2018). The biochar obtained from some SSs has low carbon content with low porous structure and high ash content. However, the co-pyrolysis of plant biomass and SS, i.e. the pyrolysis after mixing these feedstock materials, improves the yield and quality of products. This process both enhances product yield and improves product properties. For soil fertility, biochar can play a key role as a soil conditioner because of its high carbon content, and it can improve the physicochemical and biological properties of soil. Organic carbon is an organic fertilizer that can increase the water retention capacity of soil (Heikkinen et al., 2019; Sutradhar et al., 2021). For soil maintenance functionality and stability, as related to carbon dioxide removal, biochar materials need

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to resist biotic or abiotic degradation. A low pyrolysis temperature tends to create biochar with high carbon yields but with small pores and no resistance to abiotic or microbial mineralization. From woody biomass after pyrolysis at a higher temperature, the biochars appear more porous because of thermal degradation of lignocellulosic components. The biochar from SSs did not have structural pores. However, the co-pyrolysis of woody biomass with SS shown in Table 3, at various blend ratios gave more porosity, low bulk density, and high carbon content than SS for biochars (Mohamed et al., 2023). The biochar from SS and blended biochars, i.e. mixing of different biochars after separate pyrolysis, could be appropriately applied as soil nutrients to replace or substitute chemical fertilizers.

Table 3 : Synergetic effect of co-pyrolyzing sewage sludge with other biomass materials

Biomass used as co-substrate in co-pyrolysis with Sewage sludge	Synergetic effects	References
Cotton stalk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reduced potential environment risk of heavy metals in biochar -Optimized biochar pore structures -Increased biochar yield -Increased biochar aromaticity and reduced the functional groups 	(Wang et al., 2019; Z. Wang et al., 2021)
Hazelnut shell (catalytic co-pyrolysis with ZnCl ₂)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reduced potential environment risk of heavy metals in biochar -Reduced potential ecological risk index -Optimized biochar pore structures -Increased biochar specific surface area 	(Zhao et al., 2022, 2018)
Willow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reduced potential ecological risk index -Optimized biochar pore structures -Increased biochar yield -Increased biochar aromaticity and reduce the functional groups 	(Kończak et al., 2019; Kończak and Oleszczuk, 2020)
Sawdust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reduced potential environment risk of heavy metals in biochar -Reduced potential ecological risk index -Increased biochar specific surface area 	(Huang et al., 2017; Leng et al., 2018)

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Rice straw	-Reduced potential environment risk of heavy metals in biochar -Optimized biochar pore structures	(Dong et al., 2020)
Rice husk	-Reduced potential environment risk of heavy metals in biochar -Reduced potential ecological risk index -Increased biochar yield	(X. Wang et al., 2021)

4 Process condition effects on carbonization product stability

The most important thermally treated external organic matter are biochar and hydrochar. They are the products of thermochemical transformation of biomass under an oxygen-deficient or oxygen-poor atmosphere. The product of the dry pyrolytic carbonization is biochar, the product of hydrothermal carbonization in an aqueous medium is hydrochar. Biochar production is standard on a commercial scale at a TRL (technology readiness level) of 8-9 whereas hydrochar production is less advanced (TRL 6-7). Biochar is EU fertilizing product according to the Regulation EU 2019/1009 and is also subject to several national regulations. In Finland, biochars are approved fertiliser products according to a new regulation (in force from October 2023). Both biochar and hydrochar have higher carbon concentrations and lower hydrogen and oxygen concentrations than the feedstock before the transformation. The two product classes differ significantly in the stability of their carbon compounds. The mean residence time of hydrochar carbon in soil is in the range of a few years or decades rather than centuries (Gronwald et al., 2016). For efficient carbon dioxide removal (CDR) from the atmosphere, a time frame of 100 years usually is applied as threshold as also the global warming potential of greenhouse gases usually is calculated for 100 years since the Second Assessment Report of the IPCC. So, this sub-section will focus on biochar as soil amendment whereas hydrochar application is discussed in section 5.2.

The stability of biochar against biological degradation is one of the most peculiar characteristics when compared to other external organic matter that may be applied to agricultural soils. Whereas the carbon of materials like compost, digestates or manure in soil usually has mean residence times of less than 10 years, carbon from biochar may remain in soil for more than 100 up to several 1000 years. Studies of earlier charcoal production sites or from Terra Preta plots in Amazonia have shown that the

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positive effects of the biochar amendment on soil characteristics may persist for centuries and biochar still can be detected in the amended soils (Glaser and Birk, 2012). The longevity of biochar-carbon in soil still sometimes is a matter of debate although already in the early biochar literature there is plenty of evidence for the long-term persistence of biochar carbon (Singh et al., 2012). Based on a 5-years incubation study, these authors found that the mean residence time of biochar carbon in soil varied between 90 and 1600 years. This large variability is partly caused by the different input materials, partly by the processing conditions.

Although a stable biochar can be produced from most biomass materials, the highest stabilities can be found in biochar produced from high lignocellulosic input materials like woody materials and husks (Bednik et al., 2022). Food waste and straw materials produce biochars with lower residence times of carbon in soil but still well above the required 100 years. However, as (Lu et al., 2020) have shown, the addition of iron as magnetite and montmorillonite as clay mineral to the pyrolysis process increase the stability of biochar. Such modifications are a benefit for carbon sequestration but currently the carbon accounting system does not yet reward such improvements in soil carbon storage. The importance of the presence of (clay) mineral compounds during pyrolysis is also stressed by (Leng and Huang, 2018) and (Yu et al., 2021). In the studies of (Zhang et al., 2022) the impregnation of biomass with K₃PO₄ aromatization and graphitization as well as conventional stability indices. But also the clay content of the soil where biochar is incorporated plays a supporting role for the longevity of biochar carbon (Yang et al., 2022).

Temperature during pyrolysis is a further important parameter affecting the stability of the resulting biochar. Most recommendations suggest a moderate temperature for optimizing the biochar stability.

Table 4: Literature overview about pyrolysis temperature effects on biochar stability.

Pyrolysis temperature recommendation	Reference
550 °C	(Singh, Cowie, and Smernik 2012)
550 – 650 °C	(Crombie et al. 2013)
600 °C	(Manyà et al. 2014)
500 – 700 °C	(McBeath, Wurster, and Bird 2015)
600 – 700 °C	(Chen et al. 2016)
400 – 700 °C	(Leng and Huang 2018)
550 °C	(Zhang et al. 2022)

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Pyrolysis temperature recommendation	Reference
490 °C	(Bong, Selvarajoo, and Arumugasamy 2022)
600 °C	(Yang et al. 2022)
500 °C	(Liao et al. 2022)
375 – 475 °C	(Chung et al. 2023)

Averaging the temperature recommendations in Table 4, a mean pyrolysis temperature of 559 °C (median: 550 °C) is advised to produce high-stability biochar. This is a temperature that is well within the usual working range of modern pyrolysis reactors. Commercial pyrolysis units operate at 500-850 °C. Selection to the pyrolysis temperature in practice depends on a multitude of factors including the reactor design and the intended use of the other pyrolysis products (pyrolysis gas and bio-oil), e.g. to generate heat or electricity or to produce fuel or basic chemicals (Schmidt et al., 2019).

Another parameter that requires attention is the particle size. In studies of (Leng and Huang, 2018) and (Manyà et al., 2014) the use of larger particle size and the combination of higher peak temperatures resulted in the production of more stable biochar. Also, the selection of the flush gas in the reactor may exert a role on biochar stability: (Kim et al., 2021) observed that the use of CO₂ instead of N₂ produced more stable biochar. However, most commercial pyrolysis units do not use flush gases as their use at scale would be costly and purchasing gases would add additional environmental impact on biochar production (energy demand to separate, pressurize and transport those gases).

For determining the stability of biochar, standard methods rely on the molar H:C and O:C ratios in biochar, but also other, oxidation-based methods like the Edinburgh stability tool (Crombie et al., 2013), may give reliable results about a parameter that cannot be really validated in-situ on the long-term. As an alternative, (Ghysels et al., 2022) recommended the deployment of analytical pyrolysis with a Py-GC-MS combination that showed good correlation with other established stability scores.

In spite of the multitude of studies about the stability of biochar, the usually applied analytical methods from soil science or biomass analysis may still under-estimate the true lifetime of biochar carbon in soil. By applying geological methods for analysing fossil carbon like the “random reflectance method”, (Sanei et al., 2024) estimated that the majority of commercial biochars might have a time frame of millions of years for the loss of half of the carbon, based on the comparison with the properties of fossil carbonaceous materials like coal. Random reflectance does not quantify specific carbon moieties, it just allows a semi-quantitative comparison with reference materials. However, this study largely

ignores the difference in biological activity in coal deposits and soils. It remains to be seen in future studies which analytical method appears as the most appropriate to determine real long-term biochar carbon stability in soil.

5 Soil environment effects of carbonization product stability

Biochar is recognised for its recalcitrant carbon content, which resists microbial degradation, leading to increased soil carbon sequestration. Furthermore, it has the potential to enhance crop yield and soil fertility by stimulating microbial activities especially in soils with low fertility (e.g. Wang et al., 2015), while reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, particularly N₂O, in Northern latitudes (Kalu et al., 2021; 2022). While research interest in hydrochar as a soil amendment is increasing, the understanding of its potential is still limited. Like other carbonaceous materials, hydrochar has potential for water and nutrient storage, and as a carbon-rich material, it has been indicated to have a short-term effect on carbon sequestration in soils (Malghani et al., 2015).

5.1 Soil environment effects on biochar stability

The carbon content of biochar is known to vary with feedstock and production conditions, but the effects of biochar have also been shown to vary with different agricultural and environmental effects depending on climate zone (e.g. Zhang et al., 2020). At a global mean annual temperature of 14.9°C, Woolf et al. (2021) showed that of the initial C ranging from 7% (biosolids gasification) to 79% (wood pyrolysis at over 600°C), 63-82% will remain unmineralized in soils after 100 years. Lefebvre et al. (2023) presented a 100-year biochar permanence factor as a function of soil temperature (Fig. 1) based on data from Woolf et al. (2021).

Figure 1 : Adapted from Lefebvre et al. (2023): 100-year biochar permanence factor as a function of soil temperature, assuming biochar production via pyrolysis at high temperature (≥ 600 °C); based on data from Woolf et al. (2021). The bars indicate the standard errors reported in Table 5 of the same publication of Woolf et al. (2021).

Soil moisture is another significant actor in biochar degradation (e.g. Wang et al., 2016). Biochar degradation was increased under unsaturated and alternating saturated–unsaturated conditions compared to saturated conditions which was linked to an increase in carboxylic and –OH functional groups (Nguyen & Lehmann, 2009). In waterlogged environments like sediments and paddy soils, oxygen depletion increases the stability of biochar (Knicker, 2011, Wu et al., 2016). Still, biochar properties, as discussed above, are the decisive factors in biochar stability.

5.2 Soil environment effects on hydrochar stability

Despite similar reaction pathways of hydrothermal carbonization and pyrolysis, hydrochars and biochars differ significantly in their degree of aromatic condensation and, most probably regarding their residence time in soil. Hydrochar is partially carbonized and dominated by alkyl molecules, and therefore less stable than aromatic groups containing biochar in soils (e.g. Fuertes et al., 2010). A high degradability of hydrochars in soil corresponds with a large amount of hydrophilic (hydroxyl, carbonyl,

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and carboxyl) functional groups, low C/N ratio, and a low lignin content of the raw material (Eibisch et al., 2013).

Naisse et al. (2015) found that during the first weeks of incubation, the addition of hydrochar to soil stimulated the mineralization of native soil organic matter (positive priming effect). They also stated that hydrochar is almost completely mineralized after a few decades and therefore has a long-term negative C sequestration potential in soils. The application of hydrochar in the soil was found to result in higher emissions of GHGs, most likely due to increased microbial activity resulting from the easily degradable C in the hydrochar (Schimmelpfenning et al., 2014). However, Malghani et al. (2015) reported that hydrochar protects soil C from decomposition since hydrochar C gradually stabilizes after initially rapid decomposition. In their 1-year field study, hydrochar-amended soils preserved 15% more native soil organic C compared to untreated controls in fine textured soil (negative priming). They estimated a half-life of 19 years for hydrochar C (Malghani et al., 2015), indicating that the expected decadal stability of the passive hydrochar pool is much lower than expected for biochar, which could persist for centuries. Therefore, the use of hydrochar for short-term C sequestration in soils needs to be evaluated, taking into account the advantages of the hydrothermal carbonisation process, such as the use of wet feedstocks without drying (e.g. slurry manure, biowaste, sewage sludge) (Islam et al., 2021).

6 Thermochemical conversion as negative emission technology with relevance for carbon credit accounting

The production and non-oxidative use of biochar, e.g. as a soil amendment, is a negative emission technology. It is also referred to as PyCCS – Pyrogenic Carbon Capture and Storage, which also may include the use and/or storage of bio-oil and pyrolysis gas obtained during biomass pyrolysis (Schmidt et al., 2019). Currently, biochar production and use is the most relevant negative emission technology, yet it is limited by the availability of biomass.

The certification process is centred around the quantification of biochar production, biochar analysis (organic carbon content, molar H/C ratio) and the tracking of biochar including the confirmation of its soil application. Such certification schemes are offered by:

- C Capsule (Sheffield, United Kingdom)
- Puro.earth (Helsinki, Finland)
- VERRA (U.S.A., Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) Program)

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- Carbon Standards (Frick, Switzerland)

Here, we describe a typical certification process and calculate an example (taken from Hagemann, 2024). The procedures are based on the European Biochar Certificate (EBC) C-sink certificate guidelines, version 2.1 of Feb. 01st, 2021. However, they are also exemplary for comparable regulations and certifications and do not claim to be exhaustive:

Carbon footprint of biochar production

When biochar is produced from biomass (e.g., from landscaping wood) via pyrolysis, the producer is certified according to the European Biochar Certificate or the World Biochar Certificate (www.european-biochar.org). The certification process includes an on-site audit and data collection necessary to calculate biochar production's carbon expenditures (i.e., carbon footprint) in kilograms of CO₂e emitted per ton of biochar (dry matter). For example, this includes the amount of electricity and fuels needed for all operations, which includes biomass transportation to the pyrolysis unit, biomass conditioning (milling, drying, etc.), conveyors, and other auxiliary equipment of the pyrolysis unit and for (pre-)heating the pyrolysis reactor. When primary biomass is used, additional emissions would be accounted for, for example, from fertilization and land management during biomass production. However, landscaping wood is considered a secondary biomass; only emissions starting with the biomass collection are included. Concerning the emissions of the pyrolysis plant, the methane emissions are recorded. As direct methane measurements at all individual plants are too expensive, measurements from reference plants of the same model using comparable feedstock are used (certification of pyrolysis plants).

An exemplary pyrolysis plant produced 1000 t biochar within a batch¹. It caused the emission of 50 t CO₂e for biomass transportation, 200 t CO₂e for its operation (electricity, fuel), and methane equivalent to 50 t CO₂e, which sums up to 300 t CO₂e. To account for further emissions, another 10% is added as a margin of safety, resulting in 330 t CO₂e per batch or 0.33 t CO₂e t⁻¹ biochar.

All emissions must be compensated with a high-quality carbon sink certificate to achieve climate-neutral production. The IDs of the certificates used for compensation are linked to the production batch to ensure transparency of the compensation.

Carbon sink potential

A representative sample from each batch of biochar is taken and analyzed, among others, for its organic carbon and hydrogen content. The amount of organic carbon in a ton of biochar

¹ A batch is the amount of biochar produced within a maximum of 365 days under constant pyrolysis conditions, and from a constant and homogeneous feedstock.

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(dry matter) is called the carbon sink potential (unit: $t\ t^{-1}\ CO_2e$), given that all emissions caused by its productions are offset. In our example, the biochar contains 75% organic carbon ($0.75\ kg\ C\ t^{-1}$).

Tracking of biochar, biochar C sink registration

Each packaging unit of biochar receives a unique ID that allows the tracking of the biochar from its producer via traders and processors to the farmer who will apply it in his field. For this purpose, each ID is registered in a tracking system, also referred to as digital monitoring, reporting, and verification (dMRV) system. This allows the calculation of transport and processing emissions and the confirmation of the application of the biochar to the soil. Once applied to the soil, a rapid oxidation of the biochar is impossible. The ID of the biochar and the field location (GPS coordinates and/or registration number on the official land register) are used to create an entry in the C sink register. The landowner becomes the owner of the C-sink, but they may sell the rights to use the C-sink's climate effect. Once the registered C-sink certificate is used, e.g., for compensation for a flight, the C-sink certificate is marked as retired in the register.

Example

A farmer purchased 3 t of biochar with 33% moisture content, i.e., 2 t of dry matter in biochar, that was applied to his field prior to plowing the winter greening to ensure the incorporation of the biochar. Farmer confirms this in the dMRV app, which has permission to use his geolocation and the map outlining the plot to which the biochar was applied (1 ha). Then, a C-sink certificate is created and registered with $2\ t * 0.75\ t\ t^{-1}\ C_{org} * 44.01/12.011 = 5.50\ t\ CO_2e$, of which 75% ($4.13\ t\ CO_2e$.) are considered to be persistent beyond 1000 years (Schmidt et al., 2022). As transportation of the biochar from the pyrolysis facility to the field caused a total of 50 kg CO_2e emissions, the farmer uses his newly created C-sink to compensate for these emissions and the respective share of production emissions accounting for $(2\ t * 0.33\ t\ t^{-1}\ CO_2e =) 0.66\ t\ CO_2e$. The farmer retires, thus, $(0.05\ t\ CO_2e + 0.66\ t\ CO_2e =) 0.71\ t\ CO_2e$ from the persistent part of the registered C-sink and may sell the remaining $(4.13\ t\ CO_2e - 0.71\ t\ CO_2e =) 3.42\ t\ CO_2e$ on the voluntary market for emission compensation. $1.37\ t\ CO_2e$ are stored temporarily in the semi-persistent carbon pool of the biochar (Schmidt et al., 2022)

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